

Evaluating Core Size and Delayed Neutron Precursors Modeling on Molten Salt Reactor Dynamics

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ABSTRACT

Molten salt reactors (MSRs) exhibit unique dynamic behavior due to the continuous circulation of liquid fuel and the transport of delayed neutron precursors (DNPs) throughout the primary loop. These features introduce strong coupling between neutronics and thermal-hydraulics, making accurate dynamic simulation essential for assessing reactor stability and transient performance. While traditional reactor dynamics simulations rely on the standard six-group DNPs representation, the suitability of reducing or expanding these groups for MSR applications remains insufficiently understood. Recent findings indicate that expanding beyond six groups offers limited benefit for small-core configurations, whereas reducing the number of groups can introduce measurable deviations in predicted reactivity and power following transients. This study investigates the combined effects of core size and DNPs group condensation on MSR transient behavior. Two reactor configurations are analyzed: a small core similar to the Molten Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE) design and a larger core representative of the FUJI design. Simulations are performed using the zero-dimensional DYMO code and the one-dimensional multi-channel SDAT code. By comparing whole six-group models, reduced-group models, and zero-versus one-dimensional models, the work provides insight into the accuracy, limitations, and applicability of simplified precursor models in MSR dynamics. The results demonstrate how core size and precursor modeling choices influence transient-response fidelity, offering guidance for future MSR modeling strategies and tool development.

Keywords: molten salt reactors; reactor dynamics; delayed neutron precursors; reactivity loss; transient simulations.

1. INTRODUCTION

Molten salt reactors (MSRs) are among the most promising concepts within the Generation IV reactor designs [1], [2]. Unlike conventional reactors that rely on solid fuel rods, liquid-fueled MSRs use a molten-salt mixture in which fissile material is dissolved, serving simultaneously as both fuel and coolant. [3]. This design offers a suite of advantages, including inherent safety features, high thermal efficiency, and exceptional fuel utilization [4]. The ability to operate at low pressure and high temperatures, coupled with the potential for online fuel reprocessing, makes MSRs particularly attractive for future energy systems. Renewed global interest in MSRs has therefore emerged as part of the broader effort to develop advanced reactors. Significant progress is now occurring both internationally and within the United States. In northwest China, the TMSR-LF1, a 2 MW thorium-based liquid-fueled molten salt experimental reactor, achieved criticality in 2023 [5]. Meanwhile, in the United States, the Natura MSR-1 project at Abilene Christian University (ACU) is under construction and is expected to be operational in the next few years.

Unlike traditional solid-fuel reactors, MSRs involve continuous circulation of the fuel salt. This results in the drift of the delayed neutron precursors (DNPs) within the primary loop. This drift significantly

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affects reactivity feedback and, in turn, the reactor's transient response [6]. Dynamic simulations play a crucial role in understanding and predicting the time-dependent behavior of MSRs. In these dynamic studies, neutronics and thermal-hydraulic models are coupled through reactivity feedback models. Accurately capturing the unique features of these reactors requires models that can represent the transport of DNPs in the primary loop. Therefore, specialized dynamic tools are essential for evaluating the stability, safety margins, and transient performance of MSR systems under both normal and perturbed operating conditions.

Traditionally, six precursor groups are used to represent delayed neutron data in reactor dynamics simulations [7]. However, the suitability of reducing or expanding this six-group structure for MSRs is not yet fully understood, particularly given the influence of precursor drift in circulating-fuel systems. Recent studies have shown that increasing the number of groups provides no meaningful improvement in predicting the power response during initiated transients for small-core MSR configurations, while reducing the number of groups can introduce measurable deviations relative to the reference six-group model [8]. These findings highlight the need for a more systematic assessment of precursor-group representation in MSR dynamics.

In this work, the effects of core size and DNPs group reduction on MSR dynamics are systematically investigated. A small-core configuration, similar to the Molten Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE) design, and a larger FUJI reactor design are analyzed using both the reference six-group model and reduced-group representations. This comparative study evaluates the impact of spatial effects and precursor group reduction on the fidelity of MSR dynamic simulations, with the objective of identifying the minimum kinetic representation necessary to accurately capture reactor behavior and enable more efficient dynamic modeling frameworks for advanced reactor systems.

2. SIMULATION APPROACH

The Molten Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE) was used as the reference design in this study due to the availability of detailed design and kinetics data [9]. To quantify the effect of condensing the delayed neutron data, six, two, and one groups of delayed neutron data were generated through a group-condensation procedure. The effective delayed neutron parameters for the MSRE with ^{235}U fuel were used [10]. The condensation method ensures that the reduced model maintains an effective decay constant and total delayed neutron fraction (β_{eff}) consistent with the original six-group structure.

2.1. Molten Salt Reactor

The MSRE reference design was used as the baseline model, maintaining its neutronic and thermal-hydraulic characteristics. To study the influence of core size, the fuel salt residence times in the system were modified to reflect the larger geometry and shorter external loop of the FUJI-type reactor. In this study, the fuel salt transit time in the core was increased from 8.46 seconds to 28.50 seconds, while the transit time outside the core (including the hot leg, cold leg, and heat exchanger) was reduced from 16.44 seconds to 8.10 seconds. Fuel salt residence times in the tested reactor configurations are summarized in Table I. These changes were made to match the circulation characteristics of the FUJI reactor design [11] while maintaining the same mass flow rate; therefore, the difference between the MSRE and FUJI configurations primarily reflects the larger core volume of the FUJI design rather than altered operating conditions. Enabling an assessment of how increased core volume and reduced external loop time affect the distribution of DNPs and, thus, the reactivity loss.

Table I. Fuel salt residence time in the tested reactor configurations.

MSR configuration	Residence time (s)	
	Core	Out-of-core
MSRE loop	8.46	16.44
FUJI loop	28.50	8.10

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the primary loop configuration used in this study. For the thermal-hydraulics model, the whole reactor system, including the primary, secondary, and tertiary loops, was simulated to capture the coupled heat transfer and flow behavior throughout the plant. For the DNP analysis, however, only the primary loop was modeled, as precursor transport and redistribution occur exclusively within the circulating fuel salt. Tracking DNPs advection and decay along the flow path allowed us to capture their spatial redistribution and its influence on the overall reactor kinetics response.

Figure 1. Schematic of the primary loop of the simulated MSR.

2.2. Dynamics Tools

In this study, both the System Dynamics Analysis Tool (SDAT) and the Dynamics for Molten Salt Reactors (DYMOS) tools were employed to simulate the dynamic behavior of the two selected MSR configurations. While DYMOS uses a zero-dimensional point-kinetics formulation, SDAT implements a one-dimensional multi-channel model.

2.2.1. SDAT

SDAT is a flexible, physics-based simulation framework developed to model the transient behavior of advanced reactor systems with both liquid and solid fuels. Designed to balance computational efficiency with physical accuracy, SDAT provides a unified platform that captures the essential neutronic, thermal-hydraulic, and feedback interactions governing reactor dynamics. SDAT employs a one-dimensional, multi-channel formulation designed to capture the coupled neutronic and thermal-hydraulic behavior of molten salt reactors with flowing fuel. In this framework, the reactor core is discretized into axial channels, enabling the spatial evolution of fuel temperature, power distribution, and salt flow to be resolved with higher fidelity than in traditional point-kinetics models. A key feature of this approach is the explicit tracking of delayed neutron precursors as they are generated in the core, transported through the external loop, and reintroduced into the reactor. The code has been verified against MSRE reactivity insertion tests, demonstrating good agreement with the reported data [12].

2.2.2. DYMOS

DYMOS code is a robust transient and safety analysis tool specifically developed to address the unique characteristics of molten salt reactors [13], [14]. DYMOS captures circulating liquid-fuel features by adopting the point reactor kinetics equations that include the flow-out loss and flow-in gain of DNPs, based on models originally proposed at ORNL. The neutronic model is tightly integrated with a lumped-parameter thermal-hydraulic model of the primary loop, allowing the combined system to predict the evolution of reactor power, inlet and outlet temperatures, and transient salt behavior with minimal computational cost. The code has been verified against Molten Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE) startup, coast-down, and reactivity insertion tests, demonstrating good agreement with the reported data. In addition, DYMOS has been applied to large-scale molten salt reactor configurations, and its predictions of peak fuel-salt temperature are in close agreement with high-fidelity 3-D coupled RELAP5-3D/FLUENT simulations.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SDAT and DYMOS were used to simulate the MSR employing both the MSRE and FUJI primary loop configurations. First, steady-state calculations were performed to determine the reactivity loss, informed by the spatial distribution of DNPs throughout the primary loop. Second, transient simulations were conducted to assess how core size and reduced models of DNPs influence the simulated reactor response.

3.1. Reactivity Loss

The steady-state normalized distribution of the six groups of DNPs in the primary loop of the MSRE and FUJI configurations obtained using SDAT is shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3. The spatial distribution of DNPs reflects the combined effects of decay constants and fuel-salt flow. Long-lived precursor groups exhibit distributions shifted toward the upper regions of the core, as their longer half-lives allow them to be advected farther by the circulating salt. In contrast, short-lived precursor groups decay very shortly, leading to distributions that closely follow the local power profile within the core. When comparing the MSRE and FUJI primary loops, a significant fraction of DNPs is lost in the MSRE configuration due to its shorter fuel-salt transit time. Consequently, the MSRE design is expected to exhibit a larger reactivity loss. The above effects occur only in MSRs, where liquid fuel is circulating. Meanwhile, in solid-fuel reactors like light water reactors (LWRs), all DNPs remain within the fuel rods and decay there.

Figure 2. Steady-state distribution of DNPs in the primary loop of the MSRE configuration.

Tables II and III summarize the calculated reactivity loss for different representations of DNPs data and their relative errors with respect to the reference six-group representation for the MSRE and FUJI loops, respectively. Reducing the number of groups of DNPs led to deviations from the reference model: the single-group approximation exhibited the highest error, while the two-group representation significantly improved accuracy compared to the one-group model.

A comparison between SDAT and DYMOS shows consistent trends, though DYMOS generally predicts slightly higher reactivity-loss values for each group representation. This difference arises from the fundamental modeling approaches used in each tool. SDAT employs a one-dimensional representation of the primary loop, in which the spatial location of DNPs production and their subsequent transport with the flowing fuel salt are explicitly resolved. This preserves information on where precursors are born, how far they are advected, and how much of each group remains within the core region. In

contrast, DYMOS uses a zero-dimensional model that does not track the spatial distribution of DNP. The loss of spatial information causes the model to treat all precursors as uniformly mixed, leading to an overestimation of precursor removal from the core. As a result, DYMOS tends to slightly overpredict the associated reactivity loss compared to the spatially resolved SDAT results.

Figure 3. Steady-state distribution of DNP in the primary loop of the FUJI configuration.

Table II. Reactivity loss values and the relative error compared to the six-group model for the MSRE loop.

# of DNPs groups	SDAT		DYMOS	
	Reactivity loss (pcm)	Relative error	Reactivity loss (pcm)	Relative error
1	167.32	34.75%	162.90	19.30%
2	132.07	6.36%	143.71	5.24%
6	124.17	-	136.55	-

Table III. Reactivity loss values and the relative error compared to the six-group model for the FUJI loop.

# of DNPs groups	SDAT		DYMOS	
	Reactivity loss (pcm)	Relative error	Reactivity loss (pcm)	Relative error
1	53.11	53.01%	52.20	31.20%
2	39.22	13.00%	43.10	8.30%
6	34.71	-	39.80	-

For the FUJI loop, the reduction in the DNPs group representation led to a noticeably larger deviation from the six-group reference model than in the MSRE case. This increased sensitivity arises from the larger FUJI core volume, which leads to longer fuel-salt residence times, greater spatial separation between DNPs production and decay, and therefore a stronger dependence on accurately capturing the spatial distribution of DNPs.

3.2. Power Response to Initiated Transient

The transient behavior of the MSRE and FUJI cores was analyzed under a step reactivity insertion of $0.1\beta_{\text{eff}}$, as shown in Figure 4 and 6. Following the reactivity insertion, the reactor power increased rapidly, reaching a peak before being suppressed by the system's inherent negative reactivity feedback mechanisms. This feedback subsequently drove the power toward a new equilibrium. Across all DNPs, group representations showed a similar general shape and progression of the transient, indicating that the fundamental dynamic behavior was well captured regardless of the number of groups used.

Comparison with the reference six-group model revealed that deviations increased as the number of precursor groups decreased. The most prominent discrepancy occurred near the power peak immediately after the reactivity insertion, as shown in Figure 5 and 7. This observation indicates that while reduced-group models can approximate the overall transient behavior, their accuracy diminishes during rapid power excursions where the relative contributions of short- and long-lived precursor groups become more significant. Even so, the deviations remained moderate, suggesting that carefully applied group condensation can still be used in broader transient studies without substantially compromising accuracy.

Figure 4. Power response to a step reactivity insertion of $0.1\beta_{\text{eff}}$ in the MSRE loop.

Figure 5. Relative error in ΔP following a step reactivity insertion of $0.1\beta_{\text{eff}}$ in the MSRE loop.

Comparison of SDAT and DYMOS further highlights the effect of model dimensionality. SDAT, which employs a one-dimensional primary-loop model, resolved the fine perturbations in power caused by the re-entry of colder and hotter fuel salt into the core. These perturbations arise from spatial temperature variations and the advective transport of precursors, both of which SDAT explicitly tracks. In contrast, DYMOS uses a zero-dimensional lumped-parameter formulation, approximating transit-time effects with a first-order delay. As a result, DYMOS smooths out the fine-scale oscillatory structures associated with fuel circulation. Additionally, DYMOS includes only simplified representations of the secondary loop and heat-sink components; the absence of detailed features such as the air radiator introduces minor differences in the transient response.

Comparing the MSRE and FUJI configurations, both cores exhibited the same overall qualitative response to the initiated transient. However, the magnitude and duration of deviations from the reference six-group response differed between the two systems. In the MSRE loop, the divergence among the group-condensed models is relatively short-lived and diminishes quickly after the initial power peak. Conversely, in the FUJI loop, the deviations persist over a longer period, and the one-group model shows a noticeably prolonged lag before converging toward the reference solution. This behavior arises from the larger FUJI core volume and longer fuel-salt residence time, which enhance the effects of DNP's redistribution and thermal-hydraulic feedback during the transient. As a result, the FUJI configuration is more sensitive to the level of the DNP's group condensation, particularly in the early-to-mid stages of the transient.

Figure 6. Power response to a step reactivity insertion of $0.1\beta_{eff}$ in the FUJI loop.

Figure 7. Relative error in ΔP following a step reactivity insertion of $0.1\beta_{eff}$ in the FUJI loop.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the effects of DNP's group condensation and primary-loop configuration on the steady-state and transient behavior of MSRs. Using two independent dynamics tools, SDAT and DYMOS, the MSRE and FUJI primary loops were simulated to quantify the effects of spatial precursor transport and system dimensionality on reactor dynamics simulations.

For steady-state analysis, the larger FUJI loop exhibited lower reactivity loss than the MSRE configuration due to its longer fuel-salt residence time and higher in-core precursor retention. Reducing the number of groups of DNP's resulted in increasing deviation from the six-group reference model, with the one-group model producing the highest error. Nevertheless, the two-group model provided a notable improvement in accuracy, and the reactivity loss values remained within approximately 5–13% of the reference model, depending on the loop configuration. Consistent trends were observed between SDAT and DYMOS. However, DYMOS generally predicted slightly higher reactivity-loss values due to its zero-dimensional treatment, which cannot capture the spatial distribution of precursors and thus tends to overestimate precursor removal from the core.

Transient simulations of a $0.1\beta_{\text{eff}}$ step reactivity insertion showed that deviations between reduced-group models and the six-group reference were most pronounced near the transient power peak, with the one-group model showing the most significant divergence. SDAT's one-dimensional representation captured detailed perturbations associated with the re-entry of cold and hot fuel salt. In contrast, DYMOs smoothed these features due to its lumped-parameter formulation and simplified treatment of the secondary loop and heat sink. Comparison of the MSRE and FUJI transients revealed similar qualitative trends; however, deviations persisted longer in the FUJI configuration. This increased sensitivity stems from the larger core volume and longer fuel-salt residence time, which intensify the effects of precursor redistribution and thermal feedback during rapid transients.

Overall, the results indicate that moderate DNPs group condensation, such as reducing to a two-group representation, can be used effectively in broad transient and steady-state analyses without significantly compromising fidelity. However, applications requiring high-resolution transient behavior or accurate quantification of reactivity loss benefit from spatially resolved precursor tracking and whole six-group models of DNPs. The comparative results between SDAT and DYMOs also highlight the importance of model dimensionality in accurately capturing the dynamic response of flowing-fuel reactors.

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